

FLEXURAL BEHAVIOUR OF HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

The work discussed in this report is based on determining the strength characteristics of aluminium honeycomb sandwich composites for general structural applications. Honeycomb sandwich material is most notable for its high strength to weight ratios and improved rigidity to weight ratio compared to standard structural materials. The experimental work was concerned with determining the deflection at failure of aluminium honeycomb sandwich beams. These values were compared with theoretical values obtained using an equivalent rigidity model and a partial deflection theory model. The results indicated that the flexural behavior of the beams could be modeled mathematically within appropriate engineering accuracy

Keywords: sandwich, honeycomb, composite, analysis, computer

1. INTRODUCTION

Bonded honeycomb sandwich construction has been a basic structural concept in the aerospace industry for over thirty years [1]. Virtually every aircraft flying today depends upon the integrity and reliability offered by this structural approach. Because of the stiffness and weight advantages of sandwich construction many uses have been developed, including: many military and commercial airplanes, helicopters, space vehicles and navy ship interiors. Modern missiles and aircraft relying on the unique structural properties of sandwich composite material to obtain the high strength and rigidity with weight to reduce the amount of load and improve performance [2].

Sandwich construction is efficient structurally, due to the large stiffness achieved by spacing apart the most highly stressed elements, namely, the faces. Sandwich construction gives the highest stiffness to weight ratio of any common materials design. The basic principle of strength integrity is much the same as that of an I-beam.

The use of the composite material is becoming more widespread, particularly in the form of plates for strength and stiffness. Such plates are capable of providing light-weight construction in a variety of commercial applications ranging from railway car components to exterior and interior cladding for modern building (i.e., the cladding under the bridge crossing Myer and Daimaru shopping complex in Melbourne is constructed using honeycomb sandwich composite material).

The mechanical properties of the sandwich construction vary considerably depending on the manufacturing quality, type of adhesive used, pressure and temperature used during curing. This

has made both the testing of the sandwich specimens and a theoretical analysis necessary for the efficient design of sandwich structures.

In this work the authors will approach the analysis of sandwich beams and plates based on experimental results obtained from Four-point bending and Three-point bending tests. The objectives of the investigation were firstly, to find experimentally the deflection of honeycomb sandwich beams; secondly, to find the flexural properties of various honeycomb cores; and finally to compare experimental deflection values with available theoretical results obtained from a Partial deflection theory and an Equivalent rigidity theory. The development of the *SANDWICH* deflection analysis program (Structural Analysis and Design of Sandwich Composite Material) is based on these two theories.

2. ROLE OF A COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANEL

A sandwich composite structure is a three-layer type of structure consisting of two thin sheets of high strength and density material between which a thick layer of low strength and density is sandwiched. The two thin sheets are called faces, and the intermediate layer is the core of the sandwich. The core usually has light weight and are significantly less stiff and less rigid than the faces. In structural panel of this type, the faces resist bending moments and the plane compressive or shear forces. The shear forces normal to the plane of the panel are resisted by the core which also stabilizes the faces against buckling [1,2,3,4].

The primary structural role of the faces of a sandwich panel is to carry tensile, compressive, flexural, and shear stress resultants that act parallel to the plane of the panel. Typical forms of faces may be fabricated from sheet metal (aluminium), fiber composite panels or other varieties of polymers.

The core of a sandwich panel separates the two faces and holds them in a stable position. It provides a shear load path between faces, it stabilizes the faces against buckling, and together with the faces, it carries loads that are applied normal to the panel. The light weight core provides a distance between the two faces, because of this distance the moment of inertia of a cross-section of the sandwich skin and bending rigidity are large. In addition, the sandwich core also provides thermal or acoustical resistance or fire resistance. The core material can be made of many materials, but rigid foam and honeycomb are most common.

A great deal of effort has been spent to investigate the flexural properties of sandwich materials [1,2,4,5] to provide design data. In aerospace application the interest tends to be biased toward the buckling properties of sandwich composite material, because the buckling effect is utmost important in dynamic performance of aircraft structures. Whereas in other commercial applications (i.e. structured components of trains, trams, buses, ships or buildings) the designer is more interested in deflection and stresses because the demand on the dynamic performance is not the major interest. The author's work is based on structural application of sandwich composite material for general commercial applications. Consequently, the main interest here is on the flexural properties such as deflection and stresses rather than buckling properties.

3. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

3.1 Partial Deflection Theory Approach

Partial deflection theory assumed the deflection of a sandwich beam is due to bending of the section of the beam and the deflection due to shear deformation of the core [1,2,3]. Two approaches to the analysis of sandwich beams via partial deflection theory are possible [4,5]. The elementary theory, based on the assumption that a plane section remains plane after bending, which is appropriate for constructions having shear rigid core (such as honeycomb). A more rigorous theory based on the assumption of a shear flexible core, which is applicable for construction in which the core provides a low shear rigidity compared to the flexural stiffness of the faces. This approach is adopted for the current work.

Sandwich structures having shear rigid cores are very efficient, because rigid core provides an effective load path to carry shear from one face to the other. Hence direct stress resultants are mobilized in the faces to provide high strength and stiffness. Sandwich beams with shear flexible cores are not efficient beam structure because the core only partially effective in carrying shear from one face to the other, the resistance to bending by direct stress resultants in the faces may not be fully mobilized. The result is that the faces carry a larger share of load in bending about their neutral axes. In this report attention is restricted to the shear rigid core materials, where the analysis of honeycomb sandwich structures fall into this category.

3.2 Equivalent Rigidity Theory Approach

The exact solution for behavior of panels using partial deflection theory requires complex and lengthy calculation, even so, in many cases the mathematical solution may not exist for all boundary conditions. To overcome this problem many sandwich designers rely on an Equivalent Rigidity Theory to obtain quick "back of an envelope" solution [3,6]. Equivalent rigidity theory is being used widely for the analysis of sandwich material, especially in civil engineering and the plastics industries or other areas of engineering application where approximated results are more than adequate.

To understand Equivalent Rigidity theory consider a simple sandwich beam in which the core is reinforced by the skin material by mean of adhesive. Such a beam is made up of two materials with different elastic moduli and the components are joined in such a way that the bending strains at the material interfaces are the same in both. Therefore composite actions take place when the beam is subjected to bending. A given bending moment must therefore be taken partly by the core and partly by the skins. The bending moment may be expressed in terms of a reference modulus. If E_{Al} is the reference modulus of elasticity on which calculations are based then a term known as the *Equivalent Second Moment of Area* of the composite section may be determined. This represents the second moment of area of an equivalent beam composed of aluminium only (homogeneous beam with E_{Al}).

Thus, the calculation for stresses and strains, shear and deflection can be done in term of an equivalent beam. In such case the value computed will be correct for the material of modulus E but the apparent stress of the transformed cross-section must be multiplied by a *modular ratio* to obtain correct values. By introducing transformed flexural and extensional rigidities, solutions of multi-layered sandwich problems can be reduced to those of corresponding homogeneous plates or beams

Consequently, all analytical or numerical methods described for homogenous beams and panels are applicable to sandwich materials.

3.3 Computer Implementation of both Theories

Because of the complex mathematical procedures require for deflection calculations, the two analysis approaches described above were implemented in a personal computer based program with the acronym *SANDWICH*. This program is developed for the personal compute allowing engineers and designers to undertake preliminary calculations in a straightforward manner. In the *SANDWICH* program, the user may select which analysis to undertake and whether to analyze beams or plates or both, under various supporting and loading conditions. The sandwich construction can have up to four layers of skins material (with 2 layers on top and 2 layers on the bottom of the core).

The beam module of the *SANDWICH* program allow for the following supporting condition, (with up to three different point loads and one uniform point loads and one uniform distributed load may be applied).i.e. Simply supported beam, Cantilever beam and Fixed ends beam

For the panels modules, only simply supported panels module included in the program and the following loading condition may be analyzed: Central point load, Uniform distributed load and Line (strip) load

4. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Tests in which specimens are subject to bending have been widely used for many years for mechanical testing of sandwich composite material. The mechanical properties of the sandwich construction vary considerably depending on the manufacturing quality, type of adhesive used, pressure and temperature used during curing. This has made the testing of the sandwich specimens necessary for the efficient design of sandwich structures. Flexural tests on flat sandwich construction were conducted to determine bending and shear stiffness of the overall panel, shear modulus and shear strength of the core, and compressive or tensile strength of the skin facings.

4.1. Procedure

All testing was conducted in accordance with ASTM-C393 Standard test method for flexural properties of flat sandwich construction [7] with three-point and four point loading. For both the three-point load test and the four point load test the supporting fixture and the composite specimen were placed on the 10 ton dual tension-compression mode of the "Instron machine". The moveable cross head carriage of "Instron" was gradually lowered on top of the sandwich beam. The dial gauge was placed underneath the specimen as shown. The cross-head of the "Instron machine" was then allowed to move downward at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/s until failure in the specimen occurred. The reading from the dial gauge was independent of the plot of load versus deflection recorded by the "Instron machine". This was used to check the deflection of the specimen against reading obtain from the chart

Before actual test for each sample group, a trial test was performed to calibrate the chart, and to set appropriate chart speed, cross head speed and chart maximum load scale on the "Instron machine".

4.2 Sample Details

Three specifications covered all aluminium core and skins whilst one set of samples utilized glass fibre-epoxy prepreg skins.

The aluminium skins utilized were A15251 H34 alloy (for structural application) with a thickness of 1mm.

The cores used in all sandwich specimens were Aeroweb hexagonal cell honeycomb 0.002" foil, which are made from aluminium 3003 alloy. All dimensions are given in Imperial (British) units as they correspond to the material specifications required by the material supplier.

Three different core sizes were employed, namely 1/4", 3/8" and 3/4" inch cells, together with different skins for the facings. Details of specimen materials and experimental configurations employed are given in Table 1.

Table 1 - Test specimen details and configuration

NO	SPECIMEN TYPE DETAILS	SPAN (MM)	WIDTH (MM)	DEPTH (MM)
1	1/4" A1 Honeycomb cell 27mm thick, with Prepreg skins 0.5mm thick	320	64	30
2	3/8" A1 Honeycomb cell 22mm thick, with aluminium skins 1mm thick	320	64	24
3	3/4" A1 Honeycomb cell 18mm thick, with aluminium skins 1mm thick	320	64	20

The core was bonded to the facing plates using high peel strength epoxy adhesive, L-315 Epoxy Adhesive, curing at 300 F.[8] The samples of honeycomb core tested were prepared by the supplier. The sandwich beam specimens were cut from sandwich panels. The test pieces were cut to the dimension required by means of a steel bladed band saw to obtain clean edge conditions and dimensional accuracy

The span of all the test pieces were the same, i.e. 320mm, which is the minimum span length. Theoretically, different span length should be used depending on the test piece configuration as specified in ASTM-C393, however, due to equipment and testing constraint placed by the beam supporting fixture available at CSIRO Laboratory it was not possible to have a longer span length.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of the sandwich beam test pieces were calculated by using measured data of load versus deflection on the same test piece configuration and were used to obtain average values in calculation of the Flexural Properties. Figure 1 shows typical load versus deflection curves for the 3-point and four point bend tests. A third order polynomial with $r=0.97$ or better was used to fit a curve to the data.

Figure 1. Examples results comparing 3 and 4 point bending tests.

A comparison of the data indicated that there was little significant difference between the results for flexural stiffness. Consequently the flexural stiffness D and core shear modulus were calculated by the simultaneous solution of the deflection equations obtained from the Three-point and Four-point load tests. The calculation are based on equations established in ASTM-C393. The flexural properties for all the samples tested and theoretical results (from the *SANDWICH*) program are tabulated in Table 2. Again a third order polynomial was utilized to fit a curve to the data, with an r value of 0,97 or greater,

Table 2 - Results of Flexural properties of for 1/4", 3/8" and 3/4" Honeycomb (0.002" foil) core (theoretical average values in brackets)

NO	DESCRIPTION OF SANDWICH	Deflection mm (Theory)	Flexural Stiffness D Nm^2 (Theory)	Shear Stiffness kN (Theory)	Core Shear Stress MPa (Theory)	Facing Stress MPa Midspan (Theory)
1	1/4" Honeycomb core 27mm thick, Prepreg skins	0.723 (0.970)	303×10^6 (463.10^6)	328.9 (328.87)	0.284 (0.34)	90.5 (45.98)
2	3/8" honeycomb core 22mm thick, aluminium skins	0.757 (0.970)	1.33×10^9 (1.25×10^9)	179.3 (179.3)	0.34 (0.35)	54.348 (45.65)
3	3/4" Honeycomb core 18mm thick, aluminium skins	0.517 (0.560)	9.021×10^8 (463.3×10^8)	110.3 (388.37)	0.411 (0.34)	65.789 (45.98)

A comparison of the experimental results of beam deflection with the analytical solutions from the *SANDWICH* program based on Partial Deflection Theory and Equivalent Rigidities Theory is shown in Figures 3 and 4 respectively for aluminium honeycomb cells with either aluminium skins or prepreg skins.

Figure 2. Comparison of analytical and test results for aluminium skins

Figure 3. Comparison of analytical and test results for prepreg epoxy skins

In each case testing was undertaken in the three point bending mode. It is seen from the results that the flexural properties of the test piece under consideration that the experimental results were close to the theoretical estimated value within approximately three standard deviations (an engineering approximation).

6. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusion were drawn from the results of the investigation.

1. The flexural stiffness and the shear stiffness of sandwich specimens can best be obtained by solution of the two simultaneous equations obtained during four-point and three point tests on the same test piece under identical conditions of testing.
2. The flexural stiffness of the 3/8" honeycomb core model show good agreement (93.8%) with theoretical value calculated from the *SANDWICH* program (using Partial Deflection Theory).
3. The flexural stiffness of the 3/4" and 1/4" honeycomb core models shows 65% and 51% agreement to that of theoretically estimated value respectively. It is suggested that further tests is needed to determine the causes for the large discrepancies between actual test results and theoretical values as determined by the *SANDWICH* program using Partial Deflection Theory. It is suggested that one possible cause for the large deviation occurred was due to the span length of the specimens. The thicker core (1/4" honeycomb core models) should be tested at higher span for more consistent result.
4. The beam deflections, overall, show very good agreement compared to theoretical values from the *SANDWICH* program. The partial Deflection Theory gives better agreement while Equivalent Rigidities Theory values tend to be a fraction smaller.

7. REFERENCES

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